

GENDER EQUALITY PLAN OF THE FACULTY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORT

I. Introduction

Background and justification

In the context of the European Strategy on Gender Equality and the commitment to the Sustainable Development Goals, the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport is committed to implementing an integrated plan to eliminate gender disparities and create an equitable and inclusive university sport environment. This document is intended to provide strategic directions and concrete measures to combat stereotypes, prevent gender-based violence and promote innovation in the sporting environment.

In line with the strategic commitment of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport at West University of Timișoara (UVT) to promote and implement gender equality principles within an educational and institutional context characterized by diversity and inclusion, and considering the necessity of aligning with European and international standards in terms of institutional policies and practices, as well as in accordance with the objectives of our past European project SUPPORTER – *SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans*, funded by the European Union, the present action plan is adopted.

Through active involvement in the SUPPORTER project, the faculty has benefitted from an innovative training framework that has enabled the introduction and deepening of key concepts in gender equality, concepts that have so far been insufficiently explored in Romania and almost absent in the field of sports higher education. Among these concepts are intersectionality, inclusion, impact, innovation, and particularly the notion of gender-based violence, a term well-established at European level but not previously incorporated into the documents and policies of physical education and sport faculties in our country.

During the project's implementation period, the faculty actively participated in a series of online training sessions and workshops, tailored to the specific needs of physical education and sport, aimed at strengthening the skills of academic and administrative staff. These sessions highlighted topics such as the development of innovative gender equality plans (GEPs), prevention and response to gender-based violence and harassment, the implementation of inclusive policies, and adaptation to complex contexts, with a focus on the intersectional dimension of inequalities.

A key role was played by the in-person mutual learning workshops held in Strasbourg, Thessaloniki, and Ljubljana, which provided platforms for exchanging experiences and best practices among partner institutions. In these settings, our faculty had the opportunity to explore concrete examples of GEP implementation, discuss the challenges encountered in the educational and sports environment, and identify innovative, applicable solutions suited to our institution's context. The Ljubljana workshop, in particular, highlighted strategic directions and sustainable impact solutions, thereby strengthening our institutional capacity to develop long-term strategies.

As a result of participation in these activities, we acquired valuable knowledge and tools that allowed for the development and adoption of the Gender Equality Plan of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport at UVT. This plan not only reflects our firm commitment to promoting gender equality but also positions our faculty as a pioneer in the Romanian context of higher education in sport.

It is important to emphasize that without the SUPPORTER project, the faculty would not have had access to the resources, expertise, and collaborative framework necessary to integrate these innovative concepts into existing documents and policies. The inclusion of intersectionality and inclusion in our plan not only adds significant value at the institutional level but also creates the foundation for an equitable and open organizational culture in which diversity is recognized and respected. The concept of gender-based violence, which remains insufficiently discussed in Romanian educational and sports settings, has been brought to the forefront, enabling the identification and implementation of preventive and intervention measures adapted to the specific needs of our faculty.

Furthermore, the dimensions of impact and innovation have been integrated into our approach, facilitating the development of sustainable actions and measures with long-term effects on the educational environment. These elements, aligned with the strategic direction of the plan, position our faculty as a model of best practices both nationally and at the European level, reinforcing its role as a leader in promoting gender equality in physical education and sport.

Through this Gender Equality Plan, the objectives, responsibilities, timelines, and concrete actions necessary for the implementation of a robust, equitable, and contemporary institutional framework are established, contributing to the profound and sustainable transformation of the educational and organizational environment of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport at UVT.

Chapter I – General Provisions

Subject and Purpose of the Plan

(1) This Gender Equality Plan (GEP) is adopted with the primary objective of promoting and implementing gender equality principles in all areas of activity of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport at West University of Timișoara (UVT), in line with European and national standards, as well as the commitments undertaken within the framework of the SUPPORTER project.

(2) The plan establishes the institutional framework, concrete actions, timelines, and responsibilities to achieve a fair, safe, and inclusive educational and organizational environment.

(3) The purpose of this plan is to strengthen the organizational culture of the faculty by integrating gender equality principles into educational, administrative, and research processes, to prevent and address gender-based violence and harassment, and to ensure a respectful and inclusive professional and academic climate.

Scope of the Plan

(1) This GEP applies to all members of the academic community of the Faculty of Physical

Education and Sport, including academic staff, administrative staff, and students.

(2) The plan covers all activities conducted within the faculty, including teaching, research, administrative functions, and extracurricular activities.

- Promote equal access to all sports, academic and administrative programmes.
- Create a framework for action based on intersectional, innovative, impactful, inclusive and sport-specific principles.
- Establish a clear set of measures to prevent and penalise all forms of gender-based discrimination, harassment and violence.

Plan beneficiaries

- Students, athletes and students participating in university sports programmes.
- Coaches, referees and sports teachers.

The administrative and academic staff, researchers and management of the institution involved in the organisation and running of sports activities.

Sport federations and strategic partners involved in university sport.

Internal and external stakeholders

Internal stakeholders

Stakeholder	Objective	Channel / Method	Type of involvement
Faculty management	Getting strategic support	Reports, official meetings, workshops	Decision-making
Human Resources	Gender mainstreaming in HR policies	Meetings, internal trainings	Activ
Legal Department	Ensuring legal compliance	Formal meetings, email	Advisory
Ethics Committee	Preventing and tackling discrimination	Workshops, training sessions	Activ
FEFS Departments	Implementing equality in day-to-day activities	Direct collaboration, questionnaires	Activ
Trade union	Supporting equality in the employer-employee relationship	Regular discussions, consultations	Advisory
Student organisations	Getting young people involved in initiatives	Campaigns, trainings, social media	Activ
Communication Department	Promoting initiatives to the community	Newsletter, posters, online platforms	Informative

External Stakeholders

Stakeholder	Objective	Channel / Method	Type of involvement

Ministry of Education / Sport	Alignment with national strategies and policies	Formal reports, participation in consultations	Decision-making
Sports federations	Promoting equality in regulations and selections	Official letters, round tables	Advisory
Gender equality NGOs	Support for campaigns, expertise and resources	Partnerships, training sessions	Active
National Agency for Sport	Guidance and legislative support	Formal communication, calls for projects	Advisory
Media / Sports press	Changing public perceptions	Press releases, interviews, social media	Informative
Alumni	Role models, mentors	Invitation to events, podcasts	Informative / Active
Sponsors and partners	Getting financial support and visibility	Project presentations, partnership proposals	Advisory
International institutions	Access to funding and good practice	Projects, calls, reports	Consultative / Active
Local community	Informal support and cultural acceptance	Information campaigns, public events	Informative

II. Objectives and Fundamental Principles

The present document presents the strategic objectives formulated by the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport of the West University of Timisoara (FEFS-UVT), grouped according to the four guiding principles of the European SUPPORTER project: intersectionality, innovation, inclusion and impact, reflecting its direct contributions to the institutional transformation towards gender equality and the fight against gender-based violence in the university sport environment.

In order to create an equitable and high-performing university sport environment, the overall objectives are detailed below by distinct categories - students, academics, researchers and administrative staff - to address the specific needs of each group. These objectives and principles, broken down by category (students, academics, researchers and administrative staff), aim to create a university sport ecosystem based on equal opportunities, inclusion, combating stereotypes and promoting innovation. Through a group-specific approach, the institution aims to ensure optimal conditions for professional and personal development, eliminate discriminatory barriers and stimulate performance and creativity in all areas of activity.

General objectives:

Equal opportunities: Ensuring equal access to sports, research, training programmes and leadership positions in university sports.

Creating an inclusive environment: Promoting an open academic and sporting climate in which diversity - in terms of gender, ethnicity, ability and socio-economic status - is valued.

Combating gender stereotypes and gender-based violence: Implement clear measures to prevent and penalise any form of gender-based discrimination, harassment or violence.

Promoting innovation: Adoption of modern analytical methods and digital technologies for monitoring progress and incident reporting.

2. Specific objectives

a. Integrate Gender Equality Principles in Institutional Policies and Practices

Action 1.1: Review and update existing policies and procedures to incorporate gender equality provisions.

Action 1.2: Develop guidelines for inclusive language and practices applicable in both academic and administrative settings.

Timeline: 2025–2026

b. Increase Awareness and Understanding of Gender-Based Violence and Intersectionality

Action 2.1: Organize annual workshops and training sessions on gender-based violence (GBV), highlighting its relevance in the sports education context.

Action 2.2: Incorporate modules on intersectionality and inclusion into staff and student training curricula.

Timeline: 2026–2028

c. Foster an Inclusive and Supportive Academic Environment

Action 3.1: Establish a dedicated Gender Equality Committee within the faculty to oversee the implementation of the GEP and act as a resource center.

Action 3.2: Promote mentoring programs and inclusive initiatives that support the professional development of underrepresented groups.

Timeline: 2025–2027

Monitor and Evaluate the Impact of Gender Equality Measures

Action 4.1: Develop and implement a monitoring and evaluation framework to assess progress on GEP objectives.

Action 4.2: Publish annual reports on gender equality initiatives and their impact.

Timeline: 2025–2028

Guiding principles:

Intersectionality:

All actions will integrate the perspectives of gender, ethnicity, disability and socio-economic background to address the multiple barriers affecting diversity in sport.

Building on the intersectional approach promoted by SUPPORTER in identifying and combating gender inequalities, in particular through the development of policies that take into account multiple forms of discrimination (gender, ethnicity, disability, socio-economic status), the objectives of the ETF-UVT that respond to this category are:

- *Monitoring participation in sport activities on multiple criteria to highlight systemic barriers to equitable inclusion.*
- *Support equitable access to training and research through disaggregated data collection and tailor interventions.*
- *Annual gender equality audit with cross-cutting indicators and public reporting as a mechanism for institutional self-regulation.*

Innovation:

Building on the approach promoted by SUPPORTER of using modern technologies and advanced analytical methods to detect and correct inequalities, the objectives of the ETF-UVT that fall into this category are:

- Implement an online platform for reporting and monitoring progress on gender equality.*
- Implement zero-tolerance policies on gender-based violence, harassment and discrimination with strict reporting and intervention procedures.*
- Constantly reviewing the sports curriculum to include equality themes through interactive methods.*
- Developing research projects addressing gender inequalities in sport, using innovative analytical tools.*

Inclusion:

Based on the principles promoted by the SUPPORTER project, which supports the building of an inclusive organisational culture by involving all actors in training, active participation and collective empowerment, the objectives of the ETF-UVT are: .

- Organise recurrent awareness-raising workshops on gender and GBV prevention with the participation of the following stakeholders in sports and education: NGOs, students, teachers, coaches, trainers, administrative staff, sports community, representatives of sports federations and the Olympic Committee.*
- Ensure student representation in decision-making structures relevant to sports activities, respecting gender equality principles.*
- Continuous training of administrative staff through annual training workshops on the principle of inclusiveness with regard to gender equality and combating gender-based violence.*

Impact:

Building on the principles promoted by SUPPORTER of measurable and sustainable results, such as increasing the representation of women in sport, preventing GBV, creating effective

feedback and reporting systems, and visualising progress through clear indicators, the objectives of the ETF-UVVV are:

- *Document the evolution of women's participation in sports leadership positions of the UVT?, using the guidelines and methodologies promoted by SUPPORTER.*
- *Annual publication of a progress report on gender equality, modelled on the SUPPORTER project.*
- *Establishing a clear and effective methodology for reporting incidents of harassment and discrimination, highlighting the characteristic aspects of the 4Is (innovation, inclusion, intersectionality and impact) implemented within the SUPPORTER project.*

e) Adaptation to the sport environment:

Based on the following principles:

- emphasising the importance of tailoring interventions to the realities of the university sport environment with a focus on creating sport-specific tools and policies that respond to the needs of the actors involved - from coaches and referees to athletes and managers,
- promote professional capacity building through specialised training,
- introducing fair mechanisms in decision-making processes, creating a secure climate for all participants
- using feedback from the field to shape institutional policies.

The ETF-UVT has the following objectives:

- 1. To develop and implement a Code of Conduct for university sports staff (coaches, referees, managers), including clear standards on ethical behaviour, gender equality and prevention of harassment.*
- 2. Organise at least two annual training sessions for coaches, referees and sports coordinators with a focus on gender equality, stereotypes, gender-based violence and inclusive leadership.*
- 3. Integrate gender equity criteria in the selection regulations for representative teams, refereeing commissions and sports management positions.*
- 4. Carry out an annual assessment of sports infrastructure and programmes in terms of equity and accessibility (gender, disability, flexible timetables).*

III. Analysing the current situation and identifying needs

Analysing the current situation regarding gender equality in the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (FEFS) of the West University of Timisoara (UVT) reveals notable progress, but also specific challenges in the field of sport. In order to contextualise these findings, it is essential to link internal observations with national policies on gender equality.

National gender equality framework:

Romania has adopted various national strategies and plans to promote gender equality. For example, the Government General Secretariat's Gender Equality Plan for the period 2024-2027 emphasises the country's commitment to improving gender balance in all sectors, including education and sport. However, according to the Gender Equality Index 2024, Romania ranks last in the European Union, with a score of 57.5 out of 100, highlighting the need for further measures to reduce the existing gaps.

Gender equality in education and sport:

The National Strategy for Sport 2023-2032 recognises the importance of gender equality, proposing measures to promote the balanced participation of women and men in sport. However, the implementation of these policies faces difficulties, including in the education sector, where gender mainstreaming remains limited.

Linking national policies with the situation in the UVT FEFS:

Observations of gender imbalance in certain specialisations and positions within the UVT FEFS reflect national trends. While initiatives and strategies exist at national level, their implementation at institutional level requires specific adaptations and effective monitoring mechanisms. Thus, the FEFS UVT has the opportunity to align its practices with national objectives by developing internal policies that actively promote gender equality in all aspects of academic and sporting activity. In terms of ETUF human resources, there are a sufficient number of vacancies for academic positions that may be open for competition in the near future. As the competitions for these positions will be organised only after the implementation of the present document, according to the institutional calendar, they will respect all the recommendations proposed by the present gender equality plan, regarding the elaboration of the advertisements, the recruitment procedure, the salary, etc..

Regarding the administrative staff in the ETFF, the gender distribution shows that there is a prevalence of the female gender, with 2 female persons in the secretarial service, one of whom will retire in the next months and only one male person in the administrator position. Thus, after the release of one of the posts in the secretarial service, the competition for the remaining vacant post will apply the principles of gender equality as stipulated in this document regardless of whether the post will be addressed to a junior position or for a person with experience in the field.

Local university context

Currently, the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (FEFS) of the West University of Timisoara reflects both notable progress towards gender equality and some persistent challenges specific to the sports field, traditionally perceived as male-dominated. At the teaching staff level, there is a relatively balanced representation between women and men in

the administrative and theoretical teaching areas, but in the applied areas (coaching, physiotherapy, performance physical training), the presence of men is significantly higher.

In terms of students, the gender distribution is generally balanced in the Bachelor and Master programmes, but there is gender segregation in the choice of specialisations and sports disciplines (e.g. men dominate the contact or performance sports-oriented sections, while women are in the majority in areas such as physical education/aerobics).

At the institutional policy level, UVT has adopted a Gender Equality Plan at the general level, but its implementation at faculty level is not fully systematised. Clear mechanisms to monitor gender equity in recruitment processes, professional promotion, as well as in the allocation of resources or extra-curricular opportunities are still lacking.

In the area of research, projects and studies on the gender perspective in sport are still limited, and gender mainstreaming in curricula or research topics is ad hoc, without a coherent strategy.

At the same time, there is a lack of an active mentoring framework for female students, especially in areas such as sports leadership or performance coaching, where female representation is low.

On the other hand, there is openness and willingness on the part of staff and faculty management to develop equity initiatives, in particular through partnerships with different NGOs, Erasmus+ or other projects and thematic campaigns on specific areas.

In conclusion, although no systemic or direct discriminatory barriers are identified, gender equality within the UVT FEFS is at an early stage of awareness and strategic implementation, and more visible and structured actions are needed to turn good intentions into sustainable policies and practices. Through SUPPORTER project we were trained in order to create and implement content in our new GEP that will highly increase the awareness of our community regarding the gender equality issues and gender based violence and, also, how to combat the inequalities, in order to create a better work climate in the field of sports education in UVT-FEFS.

A thorough assessment of the university sports context is essential to inform strategies to improve gender equality and to develop an inclusive educational and sporting environment. In the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport, the analysis of the current situation must take into account aspects of sports performance and training, as well as those related to access, diversity and protection against any form of harassment or violence.

Procedure for monitoring and identifying gender inequalities - FEFS UVT

In the context of the West University of Timisoara's commitment to promoting gender equity, the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (FEFS) proposes an internal procedure for monitoring and identifying possible gender inequalities in academic, sports and organisational activity. This procedure aims primarily at detecting systemic imbalances or subtle barriers that may affect equal access to resources, functions and opportunities for women and men alike.

The first step in this procedure is the annual collection of data on gender equality, both at the level of academic and administrative staff and students. The information covered includes: gender distribution among teaching staff, access to managerial positions, distribution of

students by specialisations and study cycles, participation in international mobility, scholarships, research projects or competitive sports activities. This data is centralised by a designated Gender Equality Coordinator or a joint committee made up of faculty, human resources and student representatives.

Data was also collected on the level of knowledge on gender equality (GE) and gender-based violence (GBV). This research will continue on an annual basis in the form of an anonymised questionnaire addressed to students, teachers and administrative staff. The questionnaire tracks perceptions of fair treatment within the faculty, access to opportunities, sense of inclusion and possible experiences of discriminatory or sexist behaviour. Responses collected are statistically analysed and correlated with administrative data to identify relevant trends or discrepancies.

On the basis of this information, an internal report on the state of gender equality at the ETF has been drawn up. Based on the results, recommendations are made to address the current needs identified, such as: organising training sessions for staff, running a mentoring programme for female students from under-represented fields, reviewing selection and promotion procedures or introducing, where appropriate, equity criteria in the allocation of resources. The report is made available to the academic community for transparency. At the same time, the implementation of the recommendations is monitored on an annual basis, with adjustments to the procedure in the light of developments.

Through this initiative, the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport aims to become a model of good practice in promoting gender equity in the academic sports environment, strengthening its commitment to an inclusive, fair and balanced climate for all members of the university community.

The gender audit primarily involves collecting data disaggregated by multiple criteria such as gender, ethnicity, disability and socio-economic status. To this end, it is proposed to create a detailed questionnaire for all categories of faculty members - students, teachers, researchers and administrative staff - to highlight the needs and difficulties they face. For a continuous evaluation, it is recommended to establish an annual or biannual timetable for updating and analysing this data in order to observe developments and trends over time.

Also as part of the audit, an analysis of the gender distribution in sports disciplines and in curricular and extra-curricular activities will be carried out. This analysis aims to identify sports or training programmes with gender imbalanced participation. Depending on the results, corrective measures will be proposed, such as the introduction of incentives for the recruitment of female sportswomen, scholarships for women or dedicated support for students with special needs.

In terms of evaluating sports involvement, participation in competitions and training programmes will be analysed. The number of students taking part in domestic, national and international competitions and training programmes will be monitored. It will also track involvement in sports leadership activities - such as team managers or assistant coaches - and compare the gender distribution with relevant national or international data.

Special attention will also be paid to leadership roles within university sports clubs. An inventory of leadership positions - such as club president, sports director or head coach - will

be compiled and their gender breakdown analysed to identify any areas of unequal representation.

Identification of discrepancies will include an analysis of access to sports scholarships and mentoring programmes. It will assess the selection criteria for existing scholarships as well as the level of student awareness of these opportunities. It will also analyse how mentoring programmes are promoted and organised with a view to identifying possible barriers related to gender, ethnicity or disability.

In addition, the professional development courses and programmes offered within the faculty, such as coaching, refereeing or sports management, will be inventoried. It will analyse how these opportunities are accessed by students, teachers and researchers, with a view to applying the principles of equity and inclusion in the distribution of educational resources.

Specific challenges and needs

In the framework of the Supporter project, we identified the needs and challenges related to gender equality in the FEFS-UVT educational environment by analysing the data provided by the UVT Academic Life Barometer, as well as the resolutions issued by the university's Ethics Commission. These have provided valuable insight into the problems existing at FEFS in comparison to the rest of the UVT as well as the institutional measures taken to combat gender discrimination and to support the creation of an equitable academic environment.

We identified a lack of clear support mechanisms for people reporting cases of gender discrimination or harassment. In addition, we found that there is a need for continuous education of the whole academic community on respecting and promoting gender diversity.

Unequal representation of women in leadership and coaching positions

Lack of successful female role models:

Insufficient visibility of female coaches and team managers, which may discourage female students from aspiring to such roles.

The need to create mentoring and leadership programmes for women who want to take up leadership positions.

Persisting gender stereotypes

Limiting opportunities for certain categories of athletes and teachers:

Prejudices related to 'sports suitable for men' or 'sports suitable for women' that affect enrolment and performance.

Stereotypes that influence students' academic and career choices, limiting their development potential.

Identify sports or training programmes with unbalanced participation and implement corrective measures (e.g. Incentives for recruitment of sportswomen, scholarships or students with special needs)

The influence of stereotypes on curriculum and teaching methods:

Didactic content and examples that perpetuate traditional gender roles that are not adapted to contemporary realities and students' needs.

Lack of coherent policies to prevent and combat harassment and gender-based violence

Absence or non-enforcement of zero tolerance rules in gyms and on training pitches:

Lack of clear procedures for reporting and sanctioning cases of harassment, discrimination or gender-based violence.

Lack of awareness campaigns to inform athletes, coaches and teachers about the importance of a safe and respectful environment.

The need for a support system:

Employ or work with psychologists and counsellors specialised in dealing with cases of harassment and violence to provide immediate help to victims.

The need for an intersectional approach for students from disadvantaged backgrounds and students with special needs

Disability and poor socio-economic conditions:

Integration difficulties for students from disadvantaged backgrounds or with physical or sensory disabilities, requiring additional infrastructure and support programmes.

Lack of dedicated scholarships or partnerships with NGOs to provide financial and logistical support.

Integration in sports and academic activities:

The need to adapt the curriculum and teaching methodology to meet the diversity of needs and abilities.

Create support networks (tutors, mentors, fellow volunteers) to facilitate participation in courses, training and competitions.

Mainstreaming gender equality and inclusion topics in compulsory and optional subjects, in order to make students, researchers and teachers more aware of the diversity and needs of the academic community.

Gender and research and teaching

Aim: Mainstreaming gender equality and inclusion topics in compulsory and optional subjects, in order to make students, researchers and teachers more aware of the diversity and needs of the academic.

IV. Intervention Strategies and Implementation Measures

Intersectionality

General Intersectional Strategies

Detailed monitoring and analysis: Establish a permanent system for collecting and analysing data on gender and other social distribution, with a focus on the university sports environment.

In order to implement an effective system for monitoring and analysing in detail the gender and other social distribution in the university sport environment, it is essential to systematically collect relevant cross-sectional data through anonymous questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, focus groups and analysis of internal documents. These include basic demographic information such as gender (female, male, non-binary), age, ethnicity, nationality, region of origin (urban/rural), socio-economic status and, optionally, religion.

It is also important to identify membership of vulnerable groups, such as people with disabilities, Roma students, students from disadvantaged backgrounds, LGBTQ+ or immigrant/refugee students. In addition to these data, information can be collected on sports participation (type of sport played, level of involvement, access to facilities and resources, participation in competitions) and individual perceptions and experiences (discrimination, inclusion, institutional support, motivation and barriers). In addition, the analysis can include data on institutional frameworks such as diverse representation in leadership positions, mechanisms for reporting discrimination and sports inclusion initiatives.

Differentiated support programmes: Develop mentoring programmes and training courses tailored to the specific needs of student-athletes, coaches and teachers from under-represented groups.

Mentoring programmes

UVT's Career Counselling and Guidance Centre programme where students from disadvantaged backgrounds are guided by experienced mentors in leadership, professional development and sports inclusion.

Training and personal development courses

West Summer University programme which through an inclusive, open and diverse approach supports equal opportunities for all participants, regardless of gender, culture or educational background. The programme actively promotes diversity and inclusion by providing a platform where people from different corners of the world can learn together and contribute to an equitable exchange of ideas. In doing so, WSU not only supports academic development, but also reinforces fundamental values such as respect and acceptance of differences, fostering an educational environment that reflects global diversity.

Training courses/Workshops for teachers and coaches - focussing on inclusion, diversity and anti-discrimination intervention in sport The workshops are aimed at teachers from the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport of the West University of Timisoara and will contribute to the strengthening of gender equality principles in the field of physical education and sport. This training programme will provide teachers with the necessary tools to promote

an inclusive and equitable environment in educational activities, addressing topics such as eliminating gender stereotypes in sport, encouraging equal participation of all students and integrating gender sensitivity into the physical education curriculum. Through these workshops, teachers will learn how to create a climate of respect and diversity, ensuring that all students, regardless of gender, have the same opportunities to develop and excel in sport. In doing so, the initiative will support the formation of an academic culture that is more equitable and respectful of gender diversity, promoting more inclusive and accessible sport.

Counselling and training courses/workshops to prepare college leavers - career management, combating stereotypes and building support networks.

Mainstreaming intersectionality in sports curricula: Reviewing study modules and organising thematic seminars on the impact of stereotypes and the role of intersectionality in sport.

Intersectional Strategies Targeting Faculty Human Resource- Each measure will integrate intersectional analysis of gender, ethnicity, disability, and socioeconomic status.

Concrete strategies and measures by categories of beneficiaries

4I Strategy -Intersectionality						
Beneficiaries	Objective	Current situation	Measures to be applied and indicators	Implementation deadline		
				Short (12 months)	Medium (12-48 months)	Long (48+ months)
	Reduce difficulties for students from disadvantaged backgrounds	Awarding of social scholarships, merit scholarships for academic performance, scholarships and prizes awarded for performance in sport and related fields as well as sports allowance	Sports psychological counselling, on an anonymous basis, to help students manage competitive pressure and improve their academic and sporting performance, especially for those from vulnerable backgrounds <i>Indicator: number of students counselled</i> - implementing inclusive activities for athletes with disabilities that will ensure equitable participation for all students, regardless	x	x	x

			<p>of their social or financial status, and contribute to strengthening a respectful and inclusive university culture.</p> <p><i>Indicators: 2 annual activities dedicated to athletes with disabilities</i></p>			
			<p>Provision of sports equipment and educational materials for students who cannot afford them, so as not to disadvantage their learning</p> <p><i>Indicators: number and type of equipment, list of beneficiaries</i></p>	X	X	X
			<p>Creating transparent and non-discriminatory criteria for the award of sports and academic scholarships</p> <p><i>Indicator: set of criteria and application methodology</i></p>	X	X	X
	Integrating diversity in student sport activities	<p>1. To organise sports competitions that promote gender equality by entering mixed teams that encourage the participation of all categories of students.</p> <p>2. Organise thematic workshops and events to raise awareness of the intersections between gender and other factors (ethnicity, disabilities).</p>	<p>Diversification of guidance and counselling sessions specific to the field and the study programme (sport.uvt.ro) followed for all students, regardless of gender, ethnicity or socio-economic status, in order to facilitate access to opportunities (courses, competitions, mobility).</p> <p><i>Indicator: 1 session per year for undergraduate students and 1 session per</i></p>		X	X

			<i>year for masters and doctoral students</i>			
			Academic and sports mentoring programme, in which faculty members acting as year tutors, older year students (peer to peer teaching tutoring) or professionals in the field, including UVT alumni, guide newcomers in their academic journey <i>Indicator: 1Mentoring programme implementation methodology; activity plan</i>		x	x
			Counselling sessions in specialised career pathways for sport students, providing guidance in choosing a career path in line with the Programme of Study followed <i>Indicator: number of students counselled; planning of counselling sessions for each study programme</i>	x		
			Courses on diversity and gender equality in sport		x	x
			Introducing educational modules on diversity and gender equality in sport within the faculty curriculum, helping students to become more aware of the importance of respect for all people, regardless of			x

			gender or social background. <i>Indicator: chapters in the curriculum of the targeted subjects</i>			
	Increase the percentage of women in leadership roles representation student	Only 10% of students in such activities	Set specific targets (e.g. minimum 30% women on organising committees of sports events <i>Indicator: annual number of women involved in organising committees</i>	X	X	X
	Evaluate and support for the specific needs of disadvantaged students	Adaptation of the infrastructure (e.g.: access ramp, access for the visually impaired, description of the university locations in Brile	Adaptation of infrastructure (changing rooms, adapted toilets) for students with disabilities <i>Indicator: technical solutions implemented (10% more in the next 5 years)</i>			X
Framework Teaching, Researchers, Administrative Staff	Equal access to training and specialisation programmes	2 workshops and 1 training session for teachers were organised in which the general principles of gender equality were presented from the SUPPORTER project.	Providing annual specialised trainings to develop teaching and mentoring skills with a focus on gender equity <i>Indicator: number of training participants (M/W) knowledge gained through trainings and Workshops</i>	X	X	X
			Training sessions on intersectionality to adapt teaching and assessment methods to the diverse needs of students <i>Indicator: number of training participants (M/W)</i>	X	X	

		Encouraging teachers to include case studies and relevant examples from gender and an intersectional perspective in the curriculum <i>Indicator: newly designed teaching materials that include GE and GBV concepts</i>		X	X
administrative procedures sensitive to diversity	There are only general statistics and the data obtained after analysing the Barometer of academic life in UVT	Create a database tracking cross-cutting indicators (gender, ethnicity, disability) for equitable resource planning <i>Indicator: database completed</i>			X
	The gender distribution in management positions shows a 40% involvement of women (currently 2 out of the 5 top management positions of the ETFF are occupied by women but not the highest)	Increasing the proportion of women in senior administrative positions, including favouring access to the highest position in the institution <i>Indicator: the percentage of women managers in top management positions at institutional level (minimum 2% in the next 5 years)</i>		X	X
	There are currently no female-led research projects within the ETFF, although there have been in the past. The current situation is due to insufficient funding at national level for research projects as well as to the lack of a funding line within the national	Increase the number of women in the leadership of research teams with a target of 30% of project leaders/research teams to be women within the next 5 years. <i>Indicator: the percentage of women involved in research</i>		X	X

		<p>research programmes dedicated to Sport Science. At international level, although projects with female coordinators have been submitted, they have not been funded lately.</p> <p>There is only one senior research post at the ETF, occupied by a woman - the Director of the Research Centre for Sport Science and Physiotherapy at the ETF</p>	<p><i>management (minimum 2% in the next 5 years)</i></p>			
Re-searchers and executives teaching	Access to grants and projects Research independent of gender	<p>Encouraging implementation of projects addressing themes related to gender equality and sport - project implementation</p> <p>SUPPORTER</p> <p>Participation in national and international conferences on gender equality issues</p>	<p>Promoting the formation of diverse research teams (in terms of gender, ethnicity, socio-economic status) and ensuring access to ETFF research laboratories</p> <p><i>Indicator: number and composition (M/W) of newly formed teams</i></p>	x	x	x
			<p>Organising and/or participating in events that give visibility to women researchers and individuals from under-represented groups to encourage interdisciplinary collaboration</p> <p><i>Indicators: documents attesting participation (diplomas, articles, certificates, attestations, etc.)</i></p>	x	x	x

General Inclusive Measures:

Review institutional documents: update all regulations and communication materials to use neutral and inclusive language, eliminating gender stereotypes.

Wider accessibility: Adapt the sports infrastructure (halls, pitches, equipment) to ensure equal access and facilities adapted to the needs of students with disabilities.

Inclusive measures orientated towards the faculty's human resource:

4I Strategy -Inclusion						
Beneficiaries	Objectives	Current situation	Measures to be applied and indicators	Term of implementation		
				Short (12 months)	Medium (12-48 months)	Long (48+ months)
Students	Get the voices of Student through advisory forums	UVT's Career Counselling and Guidance Centre programme where students from disadvantaged backgrounds are guided by experienced mentors in leadership, professional development and sports inclusion. The West Summer University programme which through an inclusive, open and diverse approach supports equal opportunities for all participants, regardless of gender, culture or educational background. The programme	Creating advisory working groups where students can propose and discuss initiatives to improve equity and diversity <i>Indicators: the diversity of the working group, including disadvantage groups/representatives; documents proving the realisation of the activities (posters, advertisements, posters, flyers, etc.)</i>	x	x	x
	Processes transparent decision-making		Publication of the agenda and minutes of student council meetings, with the possibility for all students to contribute with suggestions <i>Indicators: Minutes</i>	x	x	x

		actively promotes diversity and inclusion by providing a platform where people from different corners of the world can learn together and contribute to a fair exchange of ideas. In doing so, WSU not only supports academic development, but also reinforces fundamental values such as respect and acceptance of differences, fostering an educational environment that reflects global diversity.	<i>meetings published on the website</i>			
	Climate of mutual respect:		Integration of diversity awareness and equal opportunities education modules in the curriculum. <i>Indicator: number of modules integrating diversity and gender into the curriculum and teaching materials support</i>			X
	Support for students with special needs		Organising sports and cultural events to celebrate diversity. <i>Indicators: number of events organised, Presented materials</i>	X	X	X
			Create a support system (tutors, counsellors). <i>Indicators: number and component support group</i>	X	X	X
Framework teaching	Training in inclusive teaching methods	Training workshops in the framework of the SUPPORTER Project in which the teaching and research	<i>Organise annual workshops and training sessions for teachers, focusing on creating an inclusive environment in classrooms and</i>	X	X	X

		staff of FEFS was trained on the 4 important principles: intersectionality, inclusiveness, innovation and impact, applicable in addressing gender equality in academia and sport	on sports pitches, to combat gender discrimination and encourage equal participation of all students, regardless of their social or financial background <i>Indicator: list of participants with the respect of GDPR regulation, guests, promotional materials</i>			
			Encouraging teachers to participate in interdisciplinary committees setting strategies on gender equality and inclusion <i>Indicators: list of participants in interdisciplinary committees</i>	x	x	x
	Involve-ment in committees and working groups		Induction and mentoring programmes, facilitating exchanges and peer support networks <i>Indicators: list of participants</i>			x
	Support for teachers from under-represented groups	At present, there are currently no persons employed in the ETF-UVT who declare membership of under-represented groups	Consultation with research teams in defining the themes and project selection criteria to ensure that diversity is addressed. <i>Indicators: meeting minutes</i>		x	x

Re-searchers	Integration the gender perspective in decisions about Research	Training workshops in the framework of the SUPPORTER Project in which ETF research and teaching staff were trained on the 4	Form diverse teams and ensure access to suitable research facilities <i>Indicators: number and composition (M/W) of teams</i>		x	x
	Inclusive research environment and collaborative	important principles: intersectionality, inclusiveness, innovation and impact, applicable in addressing gender equality in academia and sport	Developing and implementing inclusive language guidelines in official communications and regular diversity training sessions <i>Indicators: guidelines realised and used</i>		x	x

General Innovative Measures:

Use of technology: Implementation of a digital platform allowing the reporting of incidents of discrimination or harassment in real time, with an alert and data management system.

Simulations and practical workshops: Organisation of workshops and simulations exposing students and staff to real-life situations in the sports environment to identify and address gender challenges.

International partnerships: Establish collaborations with universities and international organisations specialised in gender equality and sport to exchange best practices and access European resources and funding.

Innovative measures orientated towards the faculty's human resources

4I Strategy - Innovation						
Beneficiaries	Objectives	The situation current	Measures to be applied and indicators	Term of implementation		
				Short (12 months)	Medium (12-48 months)	Long (48+ months)
Students	Technologies for	There is currently the Ethics	Organising the next 5 years of hackathons and			x

	training and monitoring	Committee of the university where complaints can be made but without the possibility to report online any situations of discrimination/harassment in real time.	Student competitions to provide data for developing IT solutions to improve equity in sports education <i>Indicators: list of competitions organised; list of participants with the respect of GDPR regulations,</i>			
	Digitising feedback		Creating a real-time digital feedback system where students can signal difficulties, propose ideas, or report incidents of discrimination or GBV <i>Indicators: digital platform</i>			X
	Updating existing documents	ETF Ethics Committee Code of Ethics of the UVT and FEFS Code of student rights and obligations	Introducing articles specifically addressing gender equality and GBV for students <i>Indicators: updated documents</i>	X	X	X
Framework teaching, Researchers, Staff administrative	Update documents existing	There is currently the Ethics Committee of the university where complaints can be made but without the possibility to report online any situations	Introducing articles dealing specifically with gender equality and GBV for employees <i>Indicators: Documents updated</i>	X	X	X

		of discrimination/harassment in real time. ETF Ethics Committee Code of Ethics of the UVT and FEFS				
	Analytical and digital methods in teaching	There are articles but in which systemic barriers are not addressed explicit	Analysing big data to assess student performance and identify systemic barriers (e.g., correlating performance with gender or socio-economic status). <i>Indicators: reports, analyses, articles</i>	x	x	x
	Workshops innovation GE and GBV orientated teaching	Training workshops on the principles of GE and GBV based on the 4I have been realised within SUPPORTER	Create communities of practice where teachers share their experiences of using technology for equity and diversity. <i>Indicators: list of members, list of events; list of participants</i>		x	x
Re-searchers	Projects research with component digital	At UVT level, courses on AI use have been organised but without being oriented towards GE and GBV integration	Encourage the application of artificial intelligence methods to analyse data on participation and performance in sport, disaggregated by gender and other factors to highlight intersectionality where appropriate, and encourage publication of results in prestigious journals <i>Indicators: reports, analyses, articles</i>		x	x

Impact

General Impact Measures:

Dedicated leadership programmes: Create professional development courses and programmes for women, focusing on sports management and coaching skills, with mentoring from leaders in the field.

Awareness-raising campaigns: Information and training campaigns for the entire university sports community, emphasising the importance of diversity and promoting positive models of gender leadership.

Promoting career-life balance

Impactful measures orientated towards the faculty's human resource:

4I Strategy -Impact						
Beneficiaries	Objective	Current situation	Measures to be applied and indicators	Term of implementation		
				Short (12 months)	Medium (12-48 months)	Long (48+ months)
Students/ Students sports	Participation in student decision-making structures	At the level of the FEFS, the Students' Association was created in 2024 but the activity is still in its infancy, with no clear positions of representation in the organising committees of	Creating "sports representative" positions for female students to increase their visibility and influence in organising boards and committees <i>Indicators: list students in the position of sports representative; list events</i>	x	x	x
			Set clear targets (e.g. minimum 30% women on organising		x	x

		the events, which are established for each event	committees of university sports competitions). <i>Indicator: number of female students involved in organising sports competitions</i>			
	Tailored training programmes	There is a university sports club with 11 sports sections in which FEFS students are affiliated and supported to	Create differentiated training plans that take into account gender, training level, medical conditions and socio-economic status. <i>Indicators: integrated training plans/protocols</i>	x	x	x
	Sport events thematic:	exercise their sports activity according to the field of practice, including participation in prestigious competitions in the university and extra-university environment	Annual organisation of 2 competitions with the aim of highlighting the importance of gender equality, inviting sportsmen and sportswomen from performance as successful role models with the promotion of mixed team competitions in sports where this is possible <i>Indicators: list of competitions, organising committees, list of participants, promotional materials</i>	x	x	x

	Measures for combating gender-based violence	<p>There's the UVT's GEP</p> <p>UVT and FEFS code of ethics</p> <p>SUP-PORTER Infopoint</p> <p>Workshops were organised within the SUP-PORTER project for students to present the aspects and implications of GBV</p>	<p>Development and clear communication of regulations on harassment and gender-based violence, with appropriate sanctions.</p> <p><i>Indicator: regulations developed</i></p> <p>Visual display of aspects of the GBV zero-tolerance policy in dormitories, sports halls, changing rooms and on the university's online platforms.</p> <p><i>Indicator: promotional materials</i></p> <p>Information and awareness-raising campaigns such as workshops and annual campus events discussing consent, healthy relationships and recognising bullying.</p> <p><i>Indicator: number of campaigns, list of events, list of participants, list of lecturers, list of promotional materials</i></p> <p>Organise 2 annual information sessions on</p>	x	x	x
--	--	---	---	---	---	---

			<p>recognising and preventing gender-based violence, involving student associations and student ambassadors.</p> <p><i>Indicator: list of events, list of participants, list of lecturers, promotional materials</i></p> <p>Mainstreaming the topic of gender-based violence in sports events through awareness-raising messages and discussion workshops.</p> <p><i>Indicator: list events, list of participants, list of lecturers, promotional materials, testimonial</i></p>			
Frame-work teaching	Increase the proportion of women in academic leadership positions	There is currently no such programme at ETFF level	<p>Mentoring programme between teachers with managerial experience and those in their early career</p> <p><i>Indicators: methodology of implementation of mentoring programme, list of lecturers, lists of participants, promotional materials</i></p>		x	x

	<p>Specific curriculum sport university</p>	<p>There are subjects in which the particularities of sports are presented and teaching is organised both for mixed groups of students and for separate groups of students (e.g. Girls Football) and students (e.g. Boys Rhythmic Gymnastics) without being specified in the curriculum particularities when organising mixed teams</p>	<p>The integration of modules dealing with the particularities of performance sport, the management of mixed teams and motivational strategies for athletes from diverse backgrounds. <i>Indicator: number of modules integrated in the curriculum and supporting materials</i></p>	x	x	x
	<p>Courses / Workshops specialised for coaches and referees</p>	<p>Courses / Workshops specialised for coaches and referees</p>	<p>Organising training courses and workshops for coaches and referees, with a focus on developing leadership skills, management</p>	x	x	x

			<p>and eliminating gender bias, harmonious relationships between coaches and athletes, combating GBV</p> <p><i>Indicator: list courses, programme of courses, list of participants, list lecturers, promotional materials, participation certificates/ certificate</i></p>			
			<p>Specialised workshops on topics such as fair refereeing, non-violent communication and preventing bullying in competitions</p> <p><i>Indicator: list of events, list of participants, list of lecturers, promotional materials,</i></p>	x	x	x
	Measures for combating violence gender	<p>There's the UVT's GEP</p> <p>UVT and FEFS code of ethics</p> <p>Exist SUPPORTER Infopoint</p>	<p>Training and empowerment:</p> <p>Annual sessions of training on the signs of abuse, reporting procedures and early intervention, and victim support.</p> <p><i>Indicator: list of participants, list</i></p>	x	x	

		Within the SUP-PORTER project, work-shops were organised for staff members didactic sessions in which the aspects and implications of GBV were presented	<i>lecturers, promotional materials, testimonial</i>			
			Encourage teachers to talk openly with students about the prevention of gender-based violence and provide support resources. <i>Indicators: activity report</i>	x	x	x
			Encouraging a culture of accountability, in which teachers act promptly and fairly on any form of discrimination or violence. <i>Indicator: list of events, list of participants, list lecturers, promotional materials, testimonial</i>	x	x	x
Frame-work teaching, Re-searchers, Staff	Balance between career and life personal	Barometer data on academic life in UVT	Flexible work programmes and fair distribution of administrative and teaching tasks, <i>Indicators: working time</i>	x	x	x

<p>admin- istra- tive</p>			<p><i>data, job de- scription</i> -Avoiding overload and overstretching, in particular for teachers at the beginning of their career or returning from care leave. <i>Indicators: job description</i> Support measures for equitable pro- fessional de- velopment: -partnerships on leadership training and in- stitutional mentoring to promote women in un- der-represented fields, <i>Indicator: list of events, list of participants, list of lecturers, promotional materials, testimonia</i> -granting of wage bonuses for people involved in implementing the GEP, in line with the UVT policy of dif- ferentiated sal- aries. <i>Indicator: Dif- ferentiated wage grid</i> Recruitment and assessment will be carried out by various</p>			
-----------------------------------	--	--	--	--	--	--

			<p>committees, with transparent and gender-sensitive criteria the gender dimension to prevent any form of direct or indirect discrimination.</p> <p><i>Indicators: the composition of recruitment committees, the set of criteria published and applied in the recruitment/evaluation process</i></p>			
Re-searchers	Involving women in leading research projects	<p>FEFS level there is openness on the institution on Implementation projects of research covering all topics in the field of sport science</p>	<p>Allocate special funds at institutional level for projects on gender equality and combating GBV in sport</p> <p><i>Indicators: budget allocation document for gender equality projects and combating GBV in sport</i></p>		x	x
		<p>There are 2 laboratories Research at the Centre for Research in Sport Science, Physical</p>	<p>Create annual awards for female-led research teams, with a focus on results and community impact</p> <p><i>Indicators: announcement of the prize competition, criteria for selection of prize</i></p>	x	x	x

		<p>Education and Physiotherapy: Laboratory Research Didactics in physical education and sport</p> <p>Laboratory Sport, physical education and society research that addresses research topics such as</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - physical culture, mass sport and sport for all, -social integration of people with special educational needs, -social reintegration of athletes, -sport and ethnicity, -physical education programmes, purpose and role 	<p><i>recipients, list of prizes offered, promotional materials</i></p>			
	<p>Applied research in sport university</p>	<p>Laboratory Sport, physical education and society research that addresses research topics such as</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - physical culture, mass sport and sport for all, -social integration of people with special educational needs, -social reintegration of athletes, -sport and ethnicity, -physical education programmes, purpose and role 	<p>Studying differences in performance and access by gender, disability or socio-economic status, with results to guide institutional policies.</p> <p><i>Indicators: reports, analyses, articles</i></p>	x	x	x

		of physical education in society, -physical education adapted, potential biometric But in this moment does not exist funding for projects outside the project SUPPORTER				
	Knowledge transfer to practice	There are co-operation protocols with coaches, sports managers and with federations but not specifically orientated on the activity of Research	Working with sports managers and federations for Implementation research findings into sports development plans. <i>Indicators: collaboration protocols, minutes of meetings, list of events, list of participants, supporting materials</i>	x	x	x
	Measures for combating gender-based violence	The EPG exists General UVT UVT and FEFS code of ethics Exist	Prevent bullying in the workplace Research: Developing clear codes of conduct for the teams research and university laboratories with zero tolerance		x	x

		SUP-PORTER Infopoint	rules for gender-based violence. <i>Indicator: code elaborated</i>			
		Workshops were organised within the SUP-PORTER project for teachers in which were presented aspects and GBV implications	Annual training sessions on the prevention of gender-based violence in science, with practical examples and case studies. <i>Indicators: list of participants, support materials, promotional materials</i>		x	x
			Analysing the factors that contribute to the occurrence or perpetuation of gender-based harassment and violence in sport and proposing evidence-based strategies to reduce these phenomena. <i>Indicators: reports, analyses, articles, strategies for fighting GBV</i>		x	x
Personal Administrative	Measures for combating gender-based violence	The EPG exists General UVT UVT and FEFS code of ethics Exist	Internal awareness-raising campaigns Creating materials and posters to send the message of zero tolerance to gender-based violence,	x	x	x

		Infopoint project SUP-PORTER	distributed in administrative premises. <i>Indicators: promotional materials</i>			
			Organisation of workshops with administrative staff to identify gender stereotypes and learn how to combat them <i>Indicators: list events, list of participants, list lecturers, materials support, promotional materials, participation diplomas</i>		x	x

V. Action Plan

The following structure of action is proposed for the successful implementation of GEP in the university sports environment:

Audit and Data Collection Stage:

To carry out a detailed study on the gender distribution of students, coaches, teachers and administrative staff in sport.

Organising focus groups, interviews and surveys to identify specific problems and intervention needs.

Draft a preliminary report outlining the critical points and the rationale for the proposed measures.

Planning and strategising stage:

Validation of the strategic objectives and setting of performance indicators, within an advisory board made up of representatives of the entire university sports community.

Establish a timetable of actions and a clear division of responsibilities between the departments involved.

Allocation of the financial, human and logistical resources necessary to implement the measures.

Implementation stage:

Launching awareness-raising and training campaigns, including workshops, seminars and trainings dedicated to various categories of beneficiaries (athletes, coaches, teachers).

Digital platform for incident reporting and continuous monitoring of progress to go live.

Organising thematic sports and academic events to promote gender equality and provide opportunities for exchange of experiences.

Monitoring, Evaluation and Review Phase (January - February, annually):

Implement a monitoring system for performance indicators, with regular evaluations (quantitative and qualitative) to measure the impact of interventions.

Annual review of the action plan, based on the feedback received and results achieved, updating objectives and adjusting strategies.

Present the results to the Governing Board and publish a transparent progress report on the implementation of the EPG.

VI. Recommendations and Proposals for Improving the University Sports Environment

Education and Awareness:

Integrate a compulsory gender equality education module in all sports and administrative study programmes.

Organising conferences, seminars and workshops in partnership with experts in the field of gender equality and sport.

Professional Development:

Creation of an interdisciplinary working group of internal experts and external consultants responsible for the implementation and monitoring of the GEP.

Develop a register of gender experts and sports mentors available to all members of the institution.

Strategic Partnerships:

Establishing partnerships with national and international sports federations, clubs and academic institutions for exchange of experience and access to European funding.

Work with non-governmental organisations specialised in combating gender-based violence to benefit from additional resources and expertise.

Technology Innovation:

Implementation of digital solutions (mobile apps, feedback platforms and big data analysis) for constant monitoring of performance indicators and incident reporting.

Development of tools for the automatic assessment of progress in the field of gender equality, specifically adapted to the sports environment.

Access and Infrastructure:

Adapting sports infrastructure (sports halls, pitches, equipment) to be accessible and friendly to all categories of users, including students with disabilities.

Provide dedicated facilities and resources for women's sport career development, including partnerships with clubs and applied sport research laboratories.

Define a data collection and analysis strategy:

Creation of a working group to develop the collection instruments (questionnaires, interviews, focus groups) and to establish the periodicity of the gender audit.

Establish a set of clear indicators (e.g. percentage of women in leadership positions, participation rate of students with disabilities) and a timetable for monitoring.

Developing institutional policies and procedures:

Introduce strict zero-tolerance rules on harassment and gender-based violence, displayed in sports and academic spaces.

Create an independent commission to handle cases of violence, discrimination or harassment, ensuring a fair and transparent process.

Building partnerships and pilot projects:

Working with gender equality organisations and NGOs supporting students from disadvantaged or disabled backgrounds.

Launch pilot mentoring and leadership programmes for women, as well as training for coaches and teachers to combat stereotypes.

Awareness campaigns and continuous training:

Organising workshops, seminars and public events to promote gender equality, diversity and the prevention of violence in sport.

VII. Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting

Monitoring Methodology:

Annual data collection through surveys, interviews and reports generated by the digital monitoring platform.

Quarterly evaluations to identify trends and adjust intervention strategies.

Set up a monitoring committee, composed of representatives of all stakeholders, to ensure a transparent and participatory evaluation.

Reporting and Transparency:

Produce an annual monitoring report, presented to the Management Board and published on the website.

Publish case studies and evaluation results to ensure transparency and inspire other institutions.

VIII. Final Provisions

This Gender Equality Plan shall come into force on the date of its approval by the faculty authorities and shall be binding for all activities carried out within the university sports environment. Regular review and updating of the GEP will ensure adaptation to the dynamics of legislative, social and sporting changes. The active involvement of the whole university sport community is essential for successful implementation, and interdepartmental collaboration and external partnerships will be the pillars of the continuous transformation towards an equitable and inclusive environment.

IX. Conclusions

Through the adoption and implementation of this Gender Equality Plan, the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport is committed to becoming a model of excellence in promoting an equitable, inclusive and innovative university sport environment. The document represents our long-term strategic commitment to eliminating gender inequality, combating violence and harassment and strengthening a sporting culture based on respect, diversity and performance.

Faculty of Physical Education and Sport - First Edition, [Date of entry into force]

This plan will be subject to regular review to reflect developments in the university sports environment and to ensure constant adaptation to new challenges and opportunities in promoting gender equality.